

*On determining the root-meaning of the Pre-PIE root of Latin Avis=“bird” and Latin Ovis=“sheep”: an unexpected parallel with PIE *h₂eyǵ- “goat” and PIE *h₂eyǵ- “oak”*

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January 10th, 2024

The PIE root of Latin Avis=“bird” is from the pre-PIE meaning “thrown” which led to “flying” but retained its “thrown” and additional “javelin/spear/arrow” meanings in the early but post-PIE stages of some IE branches at least, as I will detail; and the root of Latin Ovis is from pre-PIE “Driven”, as sheep are driven by shepherds; and PIE *h₂eyǵ- , “goat” is from another Pre-PIE “driven” root, and PIE *h₂eyǵ- “oak” is from “lightning”, in turn from PIE “thrown<propelled<driven”: see the known PIE root *h₂eyǵ- “to drive”, which existed alongside PIE *h₂eǵ- “to drive”.

some additional facts: Latin volo=“to fly” is derived by consensus with no dispute from PIE *g^welH- “to throw”

Ancient Greek πετάω included the meanings “to fly, to throw”

Latvian uozuols/uozals/uozuls means “oak; thunder-cloud”, and the semantic set “oak tree; lightning; to strike” is seen in a number of IE examples and probably in some non-IE languages as well, because oak trees are scientifically proven to be the trees most often struck by lightning in Europe, because of their high water content; thus oak trees were the trees of Zeus, Jupiter, Salmoxis/Zalmoxis, Thor, etc.

and thus, given the existence of the PIE root *h₂eyǵ- “to drive”, which existed alongside PIE *h₂eǵ- “to drive”, and since we find for example Sanskrit ájati=“to drive; to propel; to throw; to cast” from PIE *h₂eǵ- “to drive”

most likely PIE *h₂eyǵ-(s) “oak tree” meant “thunderbolt/lightning”, from “thrown”, from PIE *h₂eyǵ- “to drive”

and as I think has already been posited, PIE *h₂eyǵ- “goat” most likely derives from “driven” because goats are driven along by shepherds and goat-herds.

In turn, the source of PIE *h₂eyǵ- “to drive” and *h₂eǵ- “to drive” I posit had the meanings “pricking, pointed, sharp, goading”, and I will detail that more next time; for now see for example PIE *h₂eyǵ- “to sting; sharp tip; barb” and PIE *h₂eǵ- “sharp” and PIE *h₂eǵs= “axle; axle joint”; this PIE *h₂eǵs= “axle; axle joint” is already posited by Pokorny to be from “to drive” and I posit that further back it is in turn from “to goad; pointed, sharp”, which led to “to drive”.

The goat word probably carried an additional semantic referring to the goat-horns and the goat penis (“prick” is slang for penis, etc.)

The PIE root from which Latin “ovum” and English “egg” et alios derive is, in the light of the above facts, most likely from the PIE root which is the source of Latin Avis, as has already been posited, but is disputed: a vṛddhi-derivative meaning “belonging to the bird/of the bird”

The reconstructions of the roots from which Avis and Ovis derive are debated when it comes to certain important details: for example, which laryngeal did the Avis root begin with, which laryngeal did the Ovis root begin with; were the two roots identical in sound or slightly different?

Knowing/determining the exact laryngeal will enable us to be closer to determining what other PIE roots are kindred with the root of Avis and the root of Ovis: if the laryngeal was *h₃- , then the roots of Avis and Ovis are probably akin to PIE *h₃er- “to move, spring, set in motion”.

If the PIE root of Latin Avis meant “thrown”, and referred also to spears/javelins/arrows and surely also to lightning bolts, then those meanings were preserved in Pre-Proto-Albanian if not in Proto-Albanian; and in Pre-Proto-Celtic if not in Proto-Celtic: because Albanian *shotë* “big duck” derives from *sjautā , in turn from the same root as Avis, according to some linguists; and Proto-Celtic *(s)awyetos “duck” derives from the root of

Avis as well according to maybe all the experts on the subject; some linguists think that the Albanian word is an early borrowing from Balkan Celts; in which case only Celtic would be confirmed to have, according to my theory, preserved the meaning “spear” or “arrow” (“arrow” from “propelled” and “spear” from “thrown”, just as Avis=”bird” developed from “thrown”), because in various Celtic languages, the words deriving from *(s)awyetos mean “duck”, “goose”, “swan”, all birds that fly in V-formations, also known as arrow-formations.

Swans in particular were also associated with storms among the Ancient Greeks because they fly to the stormy cold north in their migration cycle, then back to Greece. The swans were associated both with the stormy north and with the mythical Utopian Hyperborea, north of the north-wind. For this reason, Zeus took the form of a swan when he seized Leda in the myth.

In Ancient Greek, the word developed the meanings “eagle” (ἄετός / αἰετός) and “bird of prey>large bird” (οἰωνός): eagles and similar raptors were the birds of Zeus, the lightning-hurler.

Albanian vita and vido mean “dove” and derive from the same root as Avis and the Ancient Greek words and the Celtic etc.: doves were associated with the oak-tree oracles of Zeus, as seen also on the Vučedol Ceramic Dove discovered in Croatia and dated to circa 2600 BC: three double-axe symbols, symbols of Zeus, are inscribed on the ancient ceramic dove’s neck.

In Armenian their word from this root (“haw”) means “bird; hen” and in Lithuanian and Latvian, their words from this root (“vista” in Latv. and “vištà“ in Lith.), mean “chicken; hen”: in these cases, the root meaning was either lost or simply not invoked/referenced, and the shift from “bird” to “chicken, hen”----and the phenomenon in many languages---but not so often in current English---of saying for example “let’s eat some bird” when the intention is specifically to eating chicken (and this is obviously the cause of the occasional semantic shift from “bird” to “chicken”)---is seen in numerous languages worldwide of various language families, including in some bird words from other IE roots.

So then what about the PIE root variously reconstructed as *h₃ew / *h₁eu- / *h₂ewH / *h₂ew- meaning “to wear; to put on clothes, to put on shoes”? If related to the root of Avis and the root of Ovis, the earlier meaning was “to bear, to carry” from “to bring along” from “to drive”: observe how Latin gero meant “to carry, to bear”, “to wear/to have on clothing”, “to have”: the meaning “to wear/have on clothing” comes from “to carry, bear”: because when you wear clothes, you are bearing them on your body and “carrying” them on your body. Another example is Armenian կրել (krel)=”to carry, to transport, to bear, to wear, to have on”.

And Old Armenian ածել (acem) means “to carry, to fetch, to bring on; to put on clothes or accessories” and no one disputes that ածել (acem) derives from PIE *h₂eg- , “to drive”.

So Michiel de Vaan I think correctly derives Latin gero from post-PIE *h₂g-es- , in turn from PIE *h₂eg- “to drive”.

The actual reality, the actual etymologies of these words, this time.
Brought to light by:

A. G., January 10th 2024

Part 2

This theory that *h₂eyg- “oak tree” derives from “lightning<thrown” and that *h₂eyg- “goat” derives from “driven” explains the hitherto unexplained tradition in Norse/Germanic, Baltic and Slavic mythology that the chariot of the storm/thunder/lightning god (Thor in the Norse tradition) was pulled by goats: since the word *h₂eyg- (“driven>goat”) was a homonym for lightning (“thrown”>”lightning”>”oak tree”).

Further than this, I will show here that *h₂eyg- , besides “thrown; to throw” and the meanings already specified above, most likely also meant “emitted; to emit”, and therefore also referred to hail, snow and rain emitted/hurled/thrown from the sky and clouds.

Adding the “emitted/to emit” shade of meaning in addition to thrown fits better the mythology of the fanged winter goat: emitting/hurling lightning, rain, hail and snow, and the winter goat---whether a he-goat or a she-goat or a hermaphrodite, is a *winter* goat---is also associated with the cold of winter (hence the fangs of the winter goat) and with the bright but seemingly (to the human on earth back then) no heat-giving sun of many partially clouded or cloudless winter days: see this quote:

“The pale winter sun which doesn't bring warmth but instead brings freezing cold (cloudy winter days are warmer than bright winter days)...In Serbia this sun is called "Zubato sunce" (Toothed Sun, Sun with teeth)...The same expression translatable to "Sun with teeth" is also found in Greece, just below Serbia and in Romania, just above Serbia...

What is the "sun with teeth"? This is the sun that causes the "frostbite", a burn-like wound which causes parts of your body to fall off...Or have to be amputated...Hence "toothed" sun which literally bites the part of your body off..."

This “biting” sun and “biting” cold is perhaps conveyed by the older root-meaning of PIE *h₂eyǵ- “sharp point”, which easily leads to “pricking” and “stabbing” and probably also “cutting”.

Since PIE *h₂eyǵ- meant “to throw, to emit” that could also have readily-enough led to the meaning “bright” (and “sharp” sometimes leads to bright, see Ancient Greek ὀξύς, which included the meanings “sharp; pointed; dazzling, bright” et al.), which is indicated directly by the Ancient Greek myth of the Aigis Gorgon, a storm being who was too bright to look upon, and also a daughter of Helios, the sun-god :

*“...the monstrous Aigis, the solar goat too bright to look at, whom the terrified Titans hid in a cave. . . Cronos's son [Zeus], once he had secured his power, made the skin of this goat into his aegis, an instrument of terror.”*²

1 [Old European culture: Tanngnjost and Tanngrisnir](#) .

2 This quote is from Philippe Borgeaud's *The Cult of Pan in Ancient Greece*, as translated by Kathleen Atlass and James Redfield. Page 100 of the 1988 edition published the University of Chicago Press. The original French edition is *Recherches sur le dieu Pan*, Institut Suisse de Rome, 1979. Borgeaud's sources for these traditions are Hyginus' *De Astronomia* (also known as/known in

“ . . . Aix was an ancient Gorgon slain by Zeus at the start of the Titan war. Zeus crafted his famed aegis shield--a goat-hide arm-guard fringed with serpents--from its skin and set her fearsome visage upon it. Aix was also memorialised amongst the stars as the constellation Capra (Greek: Aix) on the arm of Auriga. Capra's rising in late autumn heralded the onset of seasonal storms³.

Aix was a daughter of the sun-god Helios. Like the aegis-shield itself, she symbolised the storm-cloud. Her name means both "Terrible Goat" and "Fierce Storm" for the Greek word aegis contains the double-meaning of "stormy" and "goatish".

An elder Gorgon was also sometimes described as the father of the Gorgon Medousa.”⁴

the Ancient Greek word αἰγίς means: 1) the Aegis: a shield of Zeus or cloak of Athena; 2) a goat-skin coat 3) a rushing storm, hurricane 4) heart-wood/pith of the silver fir tree or of the Corsican pine; 5) a speck in the eye

meaning 1) involves both the “goat” and “storm” meanings, since the Gorgon Aix was thought of as a goat-like creature and was a storm-being as well: the goat meaning from “driven” (and maybe also “emitting (horns)”) and the “storm” from “thrower/emitter”; and the mythical being also involved the semantic shift “emitting>bright”.

meaning 2) when used that way, “a goat-skin coat”, without reference to the Aegis of the Gorgo Aix specifically, would be entirely from the “goat” meaning, which comes those earlier meanings.

Greek as the *Poeticon Astronomicon*): 2.13; and Pseudo-Eratosthenes, 1.13.

3 The constellation Capra/Aix does not actually look like a goat, and in my next update I will show more why the linguistic association caused this constellation to be seen as a goat by some IE people; if any non-IE people saw it as a goat, it was probably from the same association found in IE.

4 [GORGO AEX \(Aix\) - Goatish Monster of Greek Mythology \(theoi.com\)](http://theoi.com/gorgo-aix)

meaning 3) is completely from “thrower, emitter”, though it may possibly additionally involve a semantic “goaded>angry>an angry rushing storm” passed down as well from ancient times⁵, but I do not think that the explanation is that the root included the meanings “to move violently”, which doesn’t fit “to drive, urge on”⁶, but could fit the older meaning “goaded”: a shift from “goaded” to “moving violently” similar to the “goaded>angry” shift.

meaning 4) in Theophrastus’ *Enquiry into Plants*, the word αἰγίς refers to the heart-wood/pith of the Corsican pine and, among the Arcadians, to the heart-wood/pith of the silver fir tree; see how Ancient Greek κέντρον (=“a prick, a goad; sting; quill; thorn; spur; spike; something pointed; penis”) came to refer to a point, and to the center of a circle (the English word “center” derives from Ancient Greek κέντρον). So the meaning “heartwood, central pithy kernel” of these pine trees surely comes from “the central point”, in turn from aig=“a sharp point”. Again, compare PIE **h₂eyǵ-* “to drive” to PIE **h₂eyk̑* = “to sting; sharp tip; barb”; and again compare PIE **h₂eyǵ-* “to drive” to PIE **h₂ek̑* (=“sharp”).

5 In the 2023 version of my work on the Moesian Kjolem inscription---maybe even in 2022, I will check my uploads on Zenodo for the records of the 3 different versions of that paper that I wrote in 2022—I suggested, in addition to “angry>goaded” which I first published in 2022—that if the meanings “a rushing storm, hurricane” might derived from a likening of a storm to the terror of the Aegis, then the terror of the Aegis could be from Aig- conveying the meaning “frightening” (frightening like the Gorgon), in turn from “stiff”, which I believed was part of the semantic of the root since the root-meaning was “sharp point”, and sharp-pointed things are stiff: like the quills of a porcupine being likened to a person’s hair-standing on end when they’re scared; I also was thinking that, since that which is stiff is not soft, it is in the range of strong, and often stiff objects are strong, very strong: so I was thinking that “powerful, strong” may also be involved in the “rushing storm, hurricane” meanings, but I did not think that and did not write that “powerful, strong” would be able to account for the meanings “rushing storm, hurricane” on their own; and now I do not even think that in Ancient Greek or even Proto-Greek any meaning of “powerful, strong” was conveyed by the Aig- stem per se. The “sharp point>stiff>frightening” hypothesis still seems possible, but I think “Thrower, emitter” is much better, and better than the “sharp point>goaded>angry>rushing storm, hurricane” theory as well. The 1940 LJS suggests that the meaning “a rushing storm, hurricane” is from the terror/impressiveness of the storm being compared to the aegis, which would be from “goat”: clearly that scenario is unsatisfactory and is also in ignorance of the root-meanings from where “goat” developed.

6 I will though have to see whether any words certainly meaning “to move violently” have been found to derive from PIE **h₂eyǵ-* / **h₂eyg* (if an unpalatalized variant existed) / **h₂eyǵ-* “to drive, urge on”.

Meaning 5) “a speck in the eye”: surely from “point”.

Before moving on to a different aspect that I want to discuss, consider these additional Ancient Greek words for more evidence for my interpretation that Aig- in many Ancient Greek words meant “a sharp point” and that in Pre-PIE, that was the meaning that led to “to drive” via “to goad”:

1) αἰγίλωψ (aigilops): four different meanings known:

a) the spiny-headed/spiny-eared plant *Aegilops ovata*;

b) the Turkey oak, *Quercus cerris*: since “*ōps*” often refers to the appearance of something, in Ancient Greek (ὤψ /*ōps*, which in Ancient Greek meant “face; eye; appearance; look” from a PIE meaning of “eye”: PIE **h₃ókʷs*, “eye”), then likely the reference is to the goat-horn-like thick bristle-like protrusions found on the acorn’s cup in this species, and also the bristles surrounding the shoot buds and the bristle-tipped leaf lobes. Some have posited that for this meaning of Aegilops, the Aigi- derives from the PIE **h₂eyǵ-* “oak” meaning, but that does not seem to work with the *ōps* portion of the word. So this meaning of the word in my judgment more likely derives from the root-meaning much further back than “oak”: from Pre-PIE **h₂eyǵ-* “sharp barb”, which led to “to goad>to drive>to propel, to throw>lightning>oak tree”: this “sharp barb” option would also chime much better with the other meanings of Aegilops; in addition, besides possibly this word, Ancient Greek has no words descending from PIE **h₂eyǵ-* “oak”, but PIE **h₂eyǵ-* “goat” is well-represented in Ancient Greek. It’s also possible that the derivation for this meaning (the Turkey Oak or instead the Valonia Oak) is from “goat”, because to me at least the thick protrusions on the acorns of this species look a lot like goat horns or thick shaggy goat hair.

c) an ulcer in the eye: likely this usage comes from the “pointed” meaning leading to “pricked, gouged”, hence “ulcer”, if not from the meaning of “point, speck” as we saw with one of the meanings of aigis, “a speck in the eye”

d) in Pliny's Natural History, 19.95, Aegilops or Aegilips refers to a type of onion/garlic/chive-like vegetable: if "ops" here refers to "appearance" as it often did in Ancient Greek, then probably there were spines on the plant; but an 1855 English translation of Pliny's Natural History suggests that the word in Pliny is Aegilips⁷, not Aegilops, so perhaps the reference was to the sharp, pungent taste.

2) αἰγίθος , αἰγινθος , αἰγίοθος=a small bird, but according to the 1940 LSJ, exactly which species/genera is unknown, but possibly it is a linnet bird, which is a type of finch; whether linnet or finch, very likely the reference was to a small bird that eats thistle seeds often, so aigi- in this bird's name very likely refers to the thorns/spines of thistle plants: such an origin from "thistle" is seen for example in French chardonneret ("goldfinch"), which derives from chardon ("thistle plant"; in the plural chardons also means "spikes"), and seen in other words for finches and finch-like birds.

Compare also Ancient Greek αἰχμή="point of a spear; point of an arrow; war; warlike spirit". Ancient Greek αἰχμή is from PIE *h₂eyk̑ (= "to sting; sharp tip; barb") which I consider to be a variant of the same root-word (expressed in at least 4 different PIE forms, as noted earlier) encountered as PIE *h₂eyǵ-, "to drive".

So "sharp point, barb" is seen in some Ancient Greek words beginning with Aigi-/Aig quite certainly.

Ancient Greek αἰγανή="hunting-spear, javelin" is more likely from "to throw" rather than from "sharp pointed".

Earlier I discussed Aigi-/Aig-/Aix words in Ancient Greek where Aigi/Aig/Aix very likely had the meaning "to throw, to emit", from "to drive" in turn from to "to goad; sharp point, barb", and I discussed how the meaning "bright" in some Aigi/Aig/Aix words could have developed from "to throw out, to emit" and/or from "sharp point">"sharp">"bright" (for this one, see Ancient Greek ὀξύς="sharp; pointed; dazzling, bright" etc.); and now I

⁷ See note 233 of Book 19, in the English translation of Pliny's Natural History done by John Bostock and Henry Thomas Riley, 1855. The translation with the notes can be read at the Perseus Digital Library, you can go to book 19 then look for note number 233.

propose an additional pathway possible: “sharp point>pointed ray of light>bright”.

Words having the meaning of “bright; radiant; shining; white” very often or sometimes derive from words meaning “something pointed; ray; beam; spike; sprout”, because shiny and bright objects give off sharp-pointed rays/beams of light.

The connection of “pointed, projecting” to “bright, gleaming, shining, glittering” is an ancient and basic connection already confirmed in Indo-European: see for example the fact that PIE *ǵʰer, “to have protrusions” is considered to be the source of PIE *ǵʰer, “to beam, to shine, to glitter”, because of the projecting rays thrown off by most shiny, bright objects/phenomena.

See also PIE *ǵʰers, “stiff, stiffly erect, to project up stiffly; surprise, fear (due to hair often standing on end when surprised or frightened)”. See Latvian *zars* = “branch; twig; tine; prong, teeth (pointed branching elements in a tool)”, already proposed⁸ to be cognate with Proto-Slavic *zořà “aurora, dawn, daybreak” with both deriving from PIE *ǵʰer, “to have protrusions”,

So I think it is possible that the Ancient Greek name for the Aegean Sea, Αἰγαῖος, derives from the idea of “light-colored/bright/radiant sea”, and not from a reference to waves (aiges in Ancient Greek meant “waves”) as has been suggested in recent times, nor from the name of a man in Greek history/mythology (Αἰγεύς) after which one legend says the Aegean sea was named: compare how in the South Slavic languages, the Aegean is called the *White Sea* (Bulgarian: *mоре/Byalo more*; Macedonian Slavic: *Belo more/Бело море*; Serbo-Croatian: *Belo more/Бело море*). Given the radiance of the Aegean waters and the linguistic information that I describe above, this is very likely.

Of course, “wavy (sea)” cannot be dismissed yet, nor can “stormy (sea)” (that Αἰγαῖος meant “stormy (sea)” is an alternative theory that I have also come up with, which I first published in 2022 in my paper on the Moesian

⁸ Posited so by Konstantins Karulis, see (1992), “zars”, in *Latviešu Etimoloģijas Vārdnīca* (in Latvian), Rīga: AVOTS .

Kjolmen inscription), but I think “Bright (sea)” is more likely, and we see that the Aix Gorgon was the daughter of Helios and she was described as too bright to look upon.

Ancient Greek αἴγλη (“radiance, gleam; splendor, glory”) is of unknown etymology, not assigned to a PIE root. I think it is likely from “to emit”, from “to throw”, from **h₂eyǵ-* = “to drive, to goad”, in turn from **h₂eyǵ-* = “sharp point”: or else from **h₂eyǵ-* = “sharp>bright”; or from **h₂eyǵ-* = “sharp point”> “ray of light”> “bright, radiant”.

I also posit (and first did so in a work I published in early summer 2023 on the etymology of Pelasgos et al.) that Ἀσγελατας, an epithet of Apollo, meant “bright” as did Αἰγλάτας (see αἴγλη above), and as I did in my work from the summer of 2023, I derive Ἀσγελατας either from PIE **h₂eyǵ-s* or from a variant of that root: more likely from **h₂eyǵ-s*.

If from **h₂eyǵ-s-*, then there was a transpositioning/transposing of the S in relation to the G sound, as we see for example with Medieval Latin *tasca* from Latin *taxare* (=taksare) and such transpositioning/transposing is seen in many other examples in IE linguistics, including Ancient Greek πόλις < πτόλις (“fortification; fortified city>city”) deriving from PIE **tpelH-*, ““fortification; fortified city>city”.

See Latin *aesculus* (the winter oak or the Italian oak) which is most likely from PIE **h₂eyǵ-s*; and I posit that the *Aescul-/Askle-* of *Aesculapius/Asclepius/Asklepios* is from **h₂eyǵ-s* as well and probably meant “bright” in those names.

I posit that Proto-Germanic **gaitis* “goat” is from “driven” and is somehow from PIE **ǵ^hey-* “to drive, move, fling”, maybe as a loanword from a Non-Germanic language: then **gaitis* / **gait* meaning “goat” would be cognate with Proto-Germanic **gaizaz*, “spear, javelin, pike”. And also cognate with “goad”, which is already posited to be from PIE **ǵ^hey-* “to drive, move, fling”.

I posit that PIE **ǵ^hey-* “winter” is from “to throw (lightning, snow, hail and rain)”. And I posit that PIE **h₁eyǵ-* “ice, frost”, is from “to throw” as well, which would make **h₁eyǵ-* an old variant of **h₂eyǵ-*. And **h₁eyH* “ice,

frost” would be another variant. Alternatively, *h₁eyg- and/or *h₁eyH “ice, frost” could be from “to prick, to stab”, which could have led to “to bite”: the biting cold, frost-bite; the stinging cold.

I posit that *kápros “he-goat, billy goat” (source of Latin capra/caper=“she-goat/he-goat”) is from a root *kVpr (V=vowel undetermined) which “sharp point; pointed and projecting”, which may be of Non-IE origin. It’s unclear whether *kápros “he-goat, billy goat” would be from “to drive”, but probably so, instead of from “penis”: both “penis” and “to drive” would be from “prick”.

This ties in to my etymology of the name of the island of Kypros, which I posit since 2021 (year of publication) referred to the long pointed horn of land projecting from the island (you can read my paper on Kypros for more evidence for that, chiefly that an alternative name for the island actually meant “horn” in Ancient Greek).

I posit that Ancient Greek κυβερνώω “to drive, to steer>to govern” derives from *kVpr “to drive”, from *kVpr = “sharp point; projecting and pointed”.

Goat horns do look lightning bolt-like to me, but I don’t know if any ancient people saw the resemblance; even if they did, I’m sure that was only a secondary motivation, not the primary for the “goat ~ lightning/storm/winter” association in Indo-European culture and language.

Part 3

I posit that Phrygian Agdos/Agdestis is from “to throw, emit; thrown” in turn from PIE *h₂eǵ, “to drive, to propel”, since mythologically Agdos/Agdestis is near-identical to the Ais Gorgon, and Agdos/Agdestis was also associated with a large meteorite found near Mount Agdos in Phrygia (“a stone thrown from the sky”)⁹.

⁹ In spring/early summer of 2023, I first published (in the form of comments on my Academia.edu profile and comments in a session at the time) that Agdos/Agdestis derives

Kubele (and its variants) likely derive from a Kub="to goad, to drive, to propel, to throw" in turn probably from "sharp point": see *κῦβερνάω* "to drive, to steer>to govern" and see Ancient Greek *κῦβηλις* =axe; cleaver; knife with which cattle were slain": slaying of bulls and cattle is associated with Cybele, and the axe word could be from "to throw" (in reference to thunder-axes/lightning bolts of the storm-god hurled from the sky; and in reference to how axes were often thrown as throwing weapons), and the cleaver word from the axe word.

And I posit that very likely Medusa, seemingly from Ancient Greek *μέδω* "to protect" in reference to the frightening Gorgon/Medusa face being used to avert evil, as gargoyles are used in the same way, may actually be the Greek interpretation/adaptation of a Pre-Greek Med- which meant "to throw, to emit", probably originally from a Pre-Greek Med-"sharp point; to goad>to drive". I posit that the Ancient Greek word *μήδεα* (with the variant *μέζεα*) meaning "penis" and of disputed/unknown etymology, is a survival of this Pre-Greek med- which meant "to throw, emit".

"To throw, to emit" is more likely than "wet" (which would refer only to rain) due to the data that I present in this paper, and due to the fact that Medusa's snakes coming out of her head obviously make hidden reference to sun rays, since the Aigle Gorgon to bright to look upon was the daughter of Helios, the sun-god; and since Medusa's ability to turn people (and animals?) to stone if one looked at her, that ability emitted/was thrown out from her eyes. So this Gorgon/Medusa/Aigle was both a storm-goddess and associated closely with the sun, her father (and the sun is the father of all storms on earth, but the sun himself had a father/creator).

Medusa's turning people into stone suggests the freezing cold of winter and the lightning/stone association¹⁰.

from a PIE **Hód(s)gʷ-o-s* / **h₃éd(s)gʷ-o-s*, "to sprout", referring to the mountain. But I think my new etymology is more likely correct.

10 besides being an elliptical reference to a man's penis hardening at the sight of an attractive woman: elliptical because Medusa was usually thought of as frighteningly ugly in appearance; but that could be only one aspect, if Cybele is another version of this goddess.

Much evidence, which I will detail more next time, suggests that Medusa is the same as the Aix Gorgon and both were a Pre-Greek goddess of lightning, storm, rain and the north pole which turns the earth.

In an ancient Greek ceramic painting found on the island of Rhodes but considered to have been crafted on the island of Kos, we see the Gorgon with 4 wings as she was often depicted, and with the usual tusks/fangs, and with swastikas and swastika-like crosses, and holding two long-necked duck-like/geese-like/swan-like birds: one of the birds has a swastika on it, the other a swastika-like cross. As indicated by the Aegis of the storm, the Aegis worn by Zeus after he defeated the Gorgon; and as indicated by the Vucedol Ceramic dove, which has the double-axe of the storm-god/goddess on its neck, I'm sure that the swastikas and double-crosses on the birds are equating the birds with lightning, since Avis derives from "thrown" and was a synonym for "lightning", and the divination by birds would therefore have been closely linked to divination by lightning.

As described earlier, swans were associated with lightning because they fly in V-formations, arrow-formations: arrows are synonyms for lightning . Swans are also associated with storms because they fly to the stormy cold north in their migration cycle, then back to Greece. The swans were associated both with the stormy north and with the mythical Utopian Hyperborea, north of the north-wind.

In Aeschylus, in his play about Prometheus, he mentions that the Graeae (sisters of the Gorgons, and who dwelt next to the Gorgons) had swan-shaped bodies, which was mostly a reference to their bent-form as old women, but the reason the swan word was used instead of another choice was due to the storm and lightning and far north associations of the swan, which is also why Zeus took the form of a swan to seize Leda.

So the reason she is holding those swan-like birds is not simply a reference to a goddess of the wild game that provides people with food.

Besides lightning and the Thunder/lightning god, the swastika was also associated with friction and fire, and with the north pole: the turning of the

earth on its axis, and with stability (the four corners of the earth-stone) within movement (the four seasons caused by the earth spinning on its axis).

The friction association of the swastika comes from striking one stone against another to produce fire, and from rubbing two sticks together to make fire, and from using a bow-drill (a bow-drill is an ancient fire-making method/tool whereby a drill formed of one hard-enough piece of wood is drilled into the socket of another, often softer piece wood: this friction creates a small coal which with great care can be blown into a flame¹¹): ancient peoples usually believed---and most likely all the ancient European people believed---that stone can produce fire because stones store lightning inside them, either because the stones themselves came down from the sky as lightning bolts---and/or because lightning bolts strike stone; either way, it was believed that stones/rocks store/hold lightning within them, and this can be released through friction.

The same idea applied to wood: trees are so often struck by lightning, and it was thought that wood from trees store the fire from lightning, and this can be released through friction.

From the friction association came the coitus association: the coitus association was most pronounced with the bow-drill method for obvious reasons, but was also associated with the friction of stones being struck against each other and the friction of two sticks being rubbed together.

See this quote:

“In the myth making traditions of a wide variety of societies, there is a convergent pattern of thought concerning the origin of fire: that a stroke of thunder can deposit fire into trees or rocks and that this fire of thunder is extracted whenever friction is applied to these materials. Oftentimes the god of the thunderbolt is pictured as being actually incarnated within the material. There are also numerous occurrences of a related line of thought, equating the friction of making fire with the friction of making love. Besides the ample documentation of

11 For much more complete and detailed instructions on how to make fire using a bow-drill/fire bow, you can look at sites such as this one: [Primitive Fire Starting: the Bow Drill : 9 Steps \(with Pictures\) - Instructables](#)

this equation in the lore of diverse societies, we may consider the formulation of the philosopher Gaston Bachelard, who views the metaphorical syntax of sexual arousal as the inspiration, as it were, for Man's discovery of how to make fire by friction. Theories aside, it can be argued that the infusion of fire into wood and stone is a sexual and anthropogonic theme in the logic of myth. What follows is an attempt to present such an argument, with special reference to the anthropogonic traditions of the Greeks. In the course of examining the pertinent myths, we shall see that the stroke of the thunderbolt may be viewed as not only destructive but also pro-creative. Furthermore, the concept of procreation can presuppose that of creation itself. ¹²

All these different associations can be excellently explained by positing that the swastika was a symbol for the thunderstones/lightning-stones on one hand, and for the force that threw those lightning bolts and thunderstones out of the sky, the same force that made the earth spin on its axis (and Latin "axis" and English "axle" and the many other IE cognates, including the Greek, are from PIE **h₂eḱs*, "axis, axle", from "to drive", from "to goad" from "sharp point/sharp tip").

This brings me to a more specific etymology for PIE **k^wetwóres* "four" ("four" is seen in the four arms of the swastika discussed above).

Part 4

I posit that PIE **k^wetwóres* "four" is from the four arms of the swastika: the swastika in more ancient times chiefly was a symbol for lightning and for stone (and wood?) which were believed to store fire from the lightning. So I posit that **k^wetwóres* originally meant "lightning-holder/lightning-keeper-lightning encloser" or "fire-holder, fire-keeper, fire-encloser".

The first part of the word, **k^we-*, I posit is from a Pre-PIE ***k^we="lightning"*, in turn from a Pre-PIE ***k^we="thrown"*, from "to propel, to drive" (likely in turn from pre-PIE ***k^we="to goad"*, from "sharp point").

¹² This quote is from [http://nrs.harvard.edu/urn-hul.ebook:CHS_Nagy.Greek_Mythology_and_Poetics.1990](http://nrs.harvard.edu/urn:hul.ebook:CHS_Nagy.Greek_Mythology_and_Poetics.1990), from Harvard University.

Especially if this ***k^we-* meant “fire”, but perhaps also if this ***k^we-* meant “lightning”, ***k^we-* may be cognate with PIE **k^wep-/ *k^wap/ *k^weh₁p-/ *k^wh₂wep-* .”to smoke, to steam, to boil”, perhaps also “to move violently”---was the root-meaning of this **k^wep-/ *k^wap/ *k^weh₁p-/ *k^wh₂wep-* root “to burn, smolder; fire” or from “to move violently” (this meaning “to move violently” for this root has already been posited in previous linguistic literature by other linguists), from “goaded/pricked”, in turn from “sharp tip, sharp point”?

This ***k^we* is likely akin to the known PIE **k^wel* “to turn, to revolve”, which would then be from “to drive, to propel” leading to “to turn, to revolve”.

And I posit that the *twóres* portion is from PIE **twerH*, “to hold, to grab, to seize, to enclose”.

The outcome of **k^wetwóres* in the meaning “four” was *τέτταρες* / *τέσσαρες* in Attic Ancient Greek; but *τέσσερες* (*tésseres*) in *Ionic*, and later Greek *τέτορες* (*tétores*)— *Doric* *πίσυρες* (*písures*) — *Epic, Aeolic* *πέσυρες* (*pésures*), *πέσσυρες* (*péssures*)—*Aeolic* *πέτταρες* (*péttares*)—*Boeotian*

and in combining form, *τετρα-/τεθρ-* (*added to a word beginning in a vowel with rough breathing*)/*τετρ-* (*added before a vowel with smooth breathing*) in standard Ancient Greek; but *πετρα-* (*petra-*) for *τετρα-* in Boeotian and *πετρο-* (*petro-*) for *tetra-* in Thessalian.

πέτρᾱ (meaning “rock/stone” and “rock formation: cliff, ridge”, etc.) and *πέτρος* (rock, stone, boulder) would be from PIE **k^wetwóres* via a variant Greek dialect such as Boeotian or Thessalian; or from a semi-Greek language; or from a Non-Greek language. Many Ancient Greek words beginning with P are known to derive from PIE roots which began with the **k^w-* sound.

Sanskrit has *cátur* (“four”) and *turīya* (“fourth”), the latter paralleled by Avestan *tūiriia* (“fourth”): if not simply clippings, the forms *turīya* and *tūiriia* could have been intended to make reference to “holder” and from

there even “firm, steadfast”: four in most if not all cultures is associated with stability, firmness: think of the square (four sides) base/foundation of a pyramid; so an earlier theory of mine was that *k^wetwóres meant “firm, hard”: but the word *k^wetwóres seems so much like a compound, that I accepted that it is a compound.

Then in Ancient Greek in the glosses of Hesychios I found a mysterious and formerly un-etymologized word *κατράγοντες*, meaning “wild bulls” in the Laconian Ancient Greek dialect. I interpret this word as *γοντες*=“bulls”, from PIE *g^wōws / *g^wéh₃-u-s =“cattle”; and *κατρά*=“wild”, a word which I derive from an earlier *κατρά*=“forest, wood” from *κατρά*=“wood, stone”, from “fire-holder” or “lightning-holder”, because, as explained above in part 3, stone and wood were believed to store lightning inside them, which could be released by friction as fire.

I posit that the name of the Satrai (Σάτραι) is a sibilized form of this *κατρά*=“wild; forest; wood; stone; mountain” in a Thracian dialect that had sibilization of the *k^w- in PIE *k^wetwóres even though many other Thracian dialects probably did not satemize that sound; see the Thracian name Ketriporis, which I think meant “Son/child of the thunderstone; Child/son of thunderwood” rather than “fourth son”: there’s no evidence that he was the fourth child or son. See also Katroso in the Kjolmen Thracian inscription which very likely meant “stone”, as I posit since 2020. In Dacian, we find *kinoúboila* while in a South Thracian idiom we find *sinupyla*, both meaning “dog apple”; the “dog” portion coming from PIE *k^wō ~ *k^wun, “dog”.

So accordingly, Satrai meant “wild”, “(of the) wood, forest, mountain”, which fits the Satrai exactly: the Satrai were a Thracian people, inhabiting part of [Mount Pangaeus](#) between the rivers [Nestus](#) (Mesta) and [Strymon](#) (Struma). According to Herodotus, they were independent in his time, and had never been conquered within the memory of man. They dwelt on lofty mountains covered with forests and snow, and on the highest of these was an oracle of Dionysus, whose utterances were delivered by a priestess¹³.

13 Herodotus, Histories: the Satrai have continued living in freedom" till his time, and "dwell on high mountains covered with forests of all kinds and snow, and they are excellent warriors". Here, they "possess the place of divination sacred to Dionysus is in their highest mountains", questioning an oracle like the one of Delphi.

They were the chief workers of the gold and silver mines in the district. Herodotus is the only ancient writer who mentions the Satrae, and Tomaschek in the 19th century regarded the name not as that of a people but of the warlike nobility among the Thracian Dii and Bessi.

A scholar important in the field of Ancient Greek culture and mythology and religion, Jane E. Harrison, identified the Satrai with the Satyri (Satyrs), the attendants and companions of Dionysus in his revels, and also with the centaurs.

There was also a Thracian tribe called the Satrokentae, according to Hecataeus (quoted in Stephen of Byzantium): I posit that Satrokentae meant “born of the wood/stone”, a reference to ancient European anthropogonic/anthropogenic myths of man arising from oak trees and stone, as mentioned in part 3 of this paper. The kentae portion would be from PIE *ken “to arise, begin”, from whence the common Thracian element -kenthos derives, usually found at the end of Thracian names, but attested as a name on its own (Kenthos) in Western Thrace.

I posit that σατύρος (satyr, lewd person) meant “wild” and has the same etymology that I posit for Satrai: but this would mean that τίτυρος (=satyr; a bellwhether ram; a reed or pipe; a common shepherd’s name) is not a reduplication of a “tur” possibly meaning “to swell”, but instead that τίτυρος meant “wild” and is from an idiom where *k^wetwóres shifted to τίτυρ-, similar to Ancient Greek τέτταρες (“four”) and similar in its terminal portion to Umbrian petur (“four”). But though “wild, forest, wood” work so excellently for σατύρος, those meanings don’t work well for these meanings of τίτυρος = “a bellwhether ram; a reed or pipe; a common shepherd’s name”.

In another paper of mine published earlier in December 2024, I gave quite different etymologies for σατύρος and τίτυρος, and that etymology semantically fits both of those very well. I refer the reader to that work of mine, which mostly deals with Thracian names ending in takos/tokos/dokos.

I posit that it's possible that the διθύρ- part of διθύρᾶμβος meant “wild” or “wood/stone” (the rest of the word may simply be a suffix); in 2022, I published a quite different etymology for διθύρᾶμβος . This new one is also likely, as were those; and this one links up with the Satyrs, the attendants of Dionysus.

In my next update I will have more new work and more details for the work here.

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2020 to January 16th, 2024